

EVALUATION OF SOYBEAN (*Glycine max.*) VARIETIES

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Abstract

Evaluation of seven genotypes was carried out for five triats in this study. Analysis of variance showed that all the genotypes were significantly different. The significantly highest yield and early flowering was observed in NRC 132 and intermediate yield was noted in four genotypes whereas MACS NRC 1667 was with relatively low yield and CO (Soy) 3 was having the lowest yield with late flowering. Among the characters reported number of pods per cluster, number of clusters per plant and number of pods per plant recorded high GCV and PCV while High PCV and moderate GCV was observed for yield. High heritability was observed with low genetic advance for all the characters except yield for which high heritability was coupled with high genetic advance. Hence selection and further inclusion in crop improvement programmes could be possible in these genotypes.

Keywords: Soybean, genetic advance, heritability, variability

Introduction

Soyabean with scientific name *Glycine max* L. is a miracle crop belonging to the family leguminosae. The crop is classified as self pollinated and the outcrossing in nature is around 0.03-6.32 per cent (Hao *et al.*, 2019). The origin of soybean is China and it is presently cultivated across the world with India ranking fifth after Brazil, USA, Argentina and China (Anonymous 2021). The worldwide production of soybean contributes to 59% of vegetable oil (USDA, 2020). In India during 2022, soyabean is cultivated in an area of 121 million ha with a production of 129 million tones (FAOSTAT 2024). In India soybean cultivated is lead by Madhya Pradesh contributing 89% of production (Anonymous 2022). Soybean serves as edible oil and protein source for both mankind and animals besides improve soil productiveness by nitrogen fixation (Worku and Astatkie, 2011). The seed contains 38 to 43% protein and 17-19% oil with inherent capacity to harbor symbiotic bacteria for nitrogen fixation and thereby enriches the soil fertility. (Chung and Singh, 2008). Soybean finds importance due to its high nutritional value as a food source for people and livestock and also serves as a source of edible oil with industrial applications. The animal feed is mostly produced with soybean as main component being rich in vegetable protein (Wang *et al.*, 2014). In Tamil Nadu the farmers are cultivating soybean after a long gap of more than fifteen years due to the requirement of poultry industry (Subramani, 2021). Evaluation of seven soybean varieties was taken up to find their suitability in Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was raised during summer 2022 at the Department of Pulses, Centre for Plant Breeding and Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. The field was located at the latitude of 11.0232°N and the longitude of 76.9293°E with an altitude

of 426.72m above MSL. The experiment plot was characterized with red soil type. The Randomized block design was followed with three replications and spacing adapted was 30cm x 10 cm. The seven varieties evaluated were NRC 132, NRC 142, NRC 147, MACS 1281, MACS 1460, MACS NRC 1667 and CO (Soy)3. The three NRC varieties were released by Indian Institute of Soybean Research, Indore, the MACS varieties were released from Agharakar Research Institute, Pune and the MACS NRC 1667 was released by collaboration of these two institutes. CO (Soy) 3 was released by Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. The observation was taken in five randomly selected plants in each of the three replications. The characters observed during the evaluation of the varieties were days to 50% flowering, plant height, number of pods per cluster, number of clusters per plant, number of pods per plant and yield per plot. The ANOVA was worked out using PB tools software version 1.3. The data was further analysed for Genotypic coefficient of variation, Phenotypic coefficient of variation, heritability and genetic advance using the software GENRBD

Results and discussion

The data was analysed for ANOVA and the mean sum of squares is provided in Table 1. It was found that all the seven genotypes differed significantly for five triats studied. The mean values along with CV value of the various characters studied for the evaluation of seven varieties is provided in Table 2. The different statistical letters are given in superscript in each column to distinguish statistically significant groups classified according to one way ANOVA test. The significantly highest yield and early flowering was observed in NRC 132 and intermediate yield was noted in four genotypes whereas MACS NRC 1667 was with relatively low yield and CO (Soy) 3 was having the lowest yield with late flowering.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for various characters in soybean

Characters	Mean sum of squares		
	Replication	Genotypes	Error
Days to fifty percent flowering	0.0476	26.0952**	0.3810
Number of pods per cluster	1.3433	16.2478**	0.8461
Number of clusters per plant	5.5205	44.6522**	0.9844
Number of pods per plant	0.0490	3.2230**	0.1335
Yield per plot	21251.1905	59434.5238*	8076.1905

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 2. Summary table of means for yield components assessed for seven genotypes

Varieties	Days to 50% flowering	Number of pods per cluster	Number of clusters per plant	Number of pods per plant	Plot yield
CO (Soy) 3	41.67 ^a	10.67 ^a	12.10 ^a	5.70 ^a	406.67 ^c
MACS 1281	37.67 ^b	4.67 ^c	4.13 ^c	4.53 ^b	683.33 ^{ab}
MACS 1460	35.33 ^c	3.87 ^c	3.33 ^c	3.00 ^c	738.33 ^{ab}
MACS NRC 1667	38.33 ^b	5.90 ^{bc}	4.80 ^c	3.80 ^{bc}	583.33 ^{bc}
NRC 132	32.67 ^d	5.87 ^{bc}	4.53 ^c	3.57 ^{bc}	843.33 ^a
NRC 142	34.67 ^c	5.23 ^c	9.13 ^b	4.00 ^{bc}	753.33 ^{ab}

NRC 147	35.33 ^c	8.13a ^b	12.13 ^a	5.67 ^a	683.33 ^{ab}
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Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Table 3 Mean, range, phenotypic (PCV) and genotypic (GCV) coefficient of variation, heritability (h²) and genetic advance (GA) for five characters in soybean

Characters	Mean	Range	PCV (%)	GCV (%)	H ² (%)	GA
Days to 50% flowering	36.52	32.67-41.67	8.19	8.02	95.74	5.90
Number of pods per cluster	6.33	3.87-10.67	38.61	35.78	85.85	4.32
Number of clusters per plant	7.17	3.33-12.13	55.01	53.23	93.66	7.61
Number of pods per plant	4.32	3.00-5.70	24.94	23.47	88.52	1.97
Yield per plot (g)	670.24	406.67-843.33	23.68	19.52	67.95	33.15

Further analysis was carried out to understand the variation and heritability found in these varieties. GCV was lesser than PCV for all the characters under study portraying the minimum influence of environmental factors for these characters. Among the characters reported number of pods per cluster, number of clusters per plant and number of pods per plant recorded high GCV and PCV. In accordance Aditya *et al.* (2011), Reni and Rao (2013) and Suresh Rao *et al.* (2014) have reported for number of pods per cluster, Baraskar *et al.* (2014) for number of clusters per plant while Shilpashree *et al.* (2021), Banerjee (2022) and Baria *et al.* (2022) have reported for number of pods per plant. High PCV and moderate GCV was observed for yield and a similar trend was reported by Mahawar *et al.* (2013)

High heritability was observed with low genetic advance for all the characters except yield for which high heritability was coupled with high genetic advance. Similarly high heritability was observed for all the traits studied by Baraskar *et al.*, (2014). High heritability was also reported by Kumar *et al.*, 2020 for number of clusters per plant and number of pods per plant. On controversy, low heritability was reported for major traits by Mofokeng, 2021.

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